

Back to the Future with Biorefineries: Bottom-Up and Top-Down Approaches toward Polymers and Monomers

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The establishment of novel biomass processing schemes is key for achieving the much-needed carbon neutrality and counteract global warming. Biomass provides a range of monomers and macromolecules with great potential to replace petro-based materials in a wide range of applications. While important developments are ongoing in the biorefinery space, cross-sectoral, multidisciplinary partnerships are paramount to speed up and de-risk the industrialization of such technologies, and an integrated view is necessary to achieve process feasibility. This perspective explores both bottom-up and top-down approaches for biomass valorization based on the main natural polymers and monomers that can be extracted or isolated from biomass. A special emphasis is put on scalability, economic feasibility, and resource availability while the biggest challenges in the path toward the development of biorefineries are also discussed.

removed by net negative emission approaches. A part of these and other greenhouse gas emissions are generated through the production of chemicals (5.2%) and the energy required for these activities (3.6%), while the majority is consumed by the energy sector (73.2%).^[2] All of these sectors strongly rely on petroleum resources.

A promising alternative to our current value chains, heavily dependent on petroleum, lies in the so-called biorefinery, which uses renewable biomass and waste streams as the source to produce valuable chemicals, materials, and fuels. Accordingly, an ideal biorefinery converts abundant, renewable, and nonedible biomass into products that are currently obtained from fossil fuels (Figure 2). The ability of biorefineries to mitigate greenhouse gas

1. Introduction

The strive for carbon neutrality has gained new momentum with the catastrophic natural events of the last years and the climate goals set by governments and companies in the near (2030) and far (2050) future. Especially the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report has highlighted the urgent need for action in all sectors of human activity if a below 2 °C scenario, with limited damage to the planet, is to be achieved.^[1] The only way to achieve this is through a combination of mitigating carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (carbon avoidance) and removing CO₂ from the atmosphere (carbon removal), as either one of these approaches alone is not enough to rapidly and effectively reduce the CO₂ emissions to the level needed (Figure 1). Furthermore, the importance of mitigating emission becomes evident in light of the globally set climate goals, as the volume of emissions (36 billion tons in 2016²) is sheer too big to be completely

emissions and supply a renewable stream of products and polymers has been heavily discussed in the literature,^[3–8] especially within more global concepts of circular economy and bioeconomy.^[9] Nonetheless, the main challenge of a biorefinery is to valorize all the different components present in biomass in a simple, viable, and energy-efficient process. For instance, typical biomass processing schemes such as pulp and paper industries target only the cellulose fraction of lignocellulosic biomass as the main product, which corresponds to ≈50 wt% of the feedstock. The remaining fractions are treated as a residue and/or a low value energy source. Other attempts focusing on only one aspect of biomass or one product, such as first- or second-generation bioethanol as fuel, have typically failed because either i) the raw material is in competition with food, ii) they only used part of the components present in biomass, or iii) the final product is of low value and requires huge volumes of material to remain cost competitive. Exceptions of course exist where legislation or subsidies have boosted these types of approaches. This problem of volume is akin to petroleum, where the 14% used to make platform chemicals^[10] bring in a significant share of the profit generated from petroleum. Therefore, a biorefinery of the future needs to use abundant and cheap (waste) streams as raw material, valorize all components of biomass, and target both high and low value applications to remain cost competitive. Furthermore, the feedstock supply must be available in large volumes throughout all seasons and have standard properties for processing—aspects that cannot be overlooked when thinking about biomass. Previous reviews have already looked in detail at net-negative emission technologies and processes or how biorefinery concepts of the past and future could look like.^[7,9,11–13]

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Figure 1. Plot showing CO₂ emissions in gigatons per year with predictions as to the different possible scenarios: business as usual (black line) and aiming at below 2 °C global warming (blue line). For the latter scenario, CO₂ emissions need to be mitigated (green space), i.e., carbon avoidance, but net negative emissions (light blue space), i.e., carbon removal, are also key to achieve this goal. Adapted with permission under Creative Commons CC BY 3.0.^[119] Copyright 2018, the Author(s). Published by IOP Science.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of an ideal biorefinery taking nonedible biomass and transforming it into chemicals, materials, and products that are currently obtained from petroleum sources. Image of tree adapted from wikimedia.com with permission under Creative Commons CC BY 3.0.

In general, Nature provides two types of natural building blocks: large macromolecules with many heteroatoms which are often insoluble and poorly processable, such as chitin, lignin, suberin, and cellulose, and smaller molecules with high carbon content and unsaturations, such as tannins, terpenes, and fatty acids, which are somewhat more soluble but are typi-

cally available in smaller amounts. Previous reviews have looked at aspects of generating polymers from biomass or renewable resources,^[5,14–16] however few have looked at an integrated view of a biorefinery as a source of polymers taking into account the feasibility from a commercial dimension.^[17,18] In the frame of this perspective and inspired by the biorefinery concept, we take

a detailed look at how and from which biomass component polymers and monomers can be obtained, as well as how such novel routes can decrease our dependency on fossil resources. We outline how existing natural macromolecules are either suitable directly for use as materials or can be transformed into platform molecules suitable for polymerization strategies (*top-down approach*). Furthermore, the use of small molecules already present in biomass (or compounds commonly occurring as derivatives from biomass processing) as building blocks for polymerizations is also explored (*bottom-up approach*). The most promising application spaces for each of these biomass components are highlighted taking into account resource availability, technological developments, and economic considerations.

2. Top-Down: Biopolymers and Their Monomers

Natural biopolymers which are extremely abundant in nature include chitin, cellulose, lignin, and suberin, and all have several aspects in common: i) composed of many heteroatoms (oxygen and nitrogen), ii) found in waste streams of established processes in the agricultural and food industry, iii) not melt-processable, i.e., they decompose before they melt, and iv) poorly soluble in common organic solvents. Especially the latter two characteristics of these natural biopolymers mean that their use as materials has so far been restricted to either niche applications, such as chitosan (obtained enzymatically from chitin) in medical applications, or low-value-high-volume uses, such as cellulose for paper and lignosulfonates as cement additives. This section will outline how each of the above-mentioned natural biopolymers can either be used as a material through modifications or how they can be deconstructed into small molecules which can then be used as monomers for polymerizations themselves.

The most abundant natural biopolymer on the planet, cellulose, has been used for centuries in the pulp and paper industry—an example of a very basic biorefinery. Alongside the classic and rather low value uses in paper, cardboard, and textile fibers, other more advanced and higher-value products have been developed such as microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), microfibrillated cellulose (MFC) or crystalline nanocellulose (CNCs). These micro- or nanosized cellulose crystals are found in applications such as personal care and food, with several companies providing CNCs and MFCs on the ton scale. Further research to improve the processability of cellulose through chemical modifications has also been performed but these have, to the best of our knowledge, not been commercialized. Alternatively, cellulose can be broken into its glucose repeating unit through chemical or enzymatic hydrolysis. Glucose itself is a fuel for any organism and is oftentimes used for fermentation into renewable platform chemicals such as alcohols or vitamins,^[19,20] which are a renewable drop-in alternative to the equivalent petroleum-based products and have already been industrialized.^[20] Another option is the modification of glucose into a polymerizable monomer, either through fermentation or chemical modifications.^[21,22] Prime examples of this are lactic acid and 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA), the monomers needed for the production of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) and poly(ethylene furanoate) (PEF), which can be obtained via fermentation, and the dehydration and oxidation of C₆ sugars,^[23] respectively. Both are or have been dealt as promising biopolymers for the replacement of commodity petroleum plastics and

are produced on an industrial scale.^[23–27] Up to date, they have not fully replaced commodity plastics because of limitations in their mechanical properties or because their production volumes are currently too low. Importantly, these developments highlight that competitive and renewable polymers can be produced from cellulose. Another commercialized glucose-derived monomer is isosorbide (**Figure 3**), which is obtained through the hydrogenation of glucose to sorbitol followed by dehydration to isosorbide.^[28,29] A variety of polymers can be made from isosorbide through polycondensation reactions with esters, carbonates, and isocyanates to form polyesters, polycarbonates, and polyurethanes with applications in the automotive and biomedical industry.^[30,31] An important note is that these polymers are most often only partially bio-based, as other monomers used are often obtained from nonrenewable resources. In addition, the before mentioned applications are rather high in value as isosorbide itself relies on several steps from biomass and is thus more expensive to produce.

Another option is to chemically modify glucose and attach or transform it into a polymerizable monomer. Notable examples include the attachment of vinyl groups for (controlled) radical polymerizations^[32,33] and its modification into cyclic monomers suitable for ring-opening polymerization.^[22] The resulting polymers have been mainly investigated from an academic perspective as typically several synthetic steps, leading to low yields and high prices, are necessary. In addition, the renewable carbon content of such monomers is typically rather low.^[34] Therefore, such macromolecules are oftentimes not suited as renewable replacements for most commodity petroleum-based polymers but are of interest for high-value applications, such as in medicine and cosmetic industries.

The second most abundant natural biopolymer on earth is chitin, with an estimated annual availability of 10 billion tons.^[35] Chitin is a macromolecule with a structure similar to cellulose (**Figure 3**), found in many organisms including fungi, arthropods, and insects. It is insoluble in most organic solvents and needs aqueous solutions below pH 6 for solubilization,^[35] meaning that the majority of studies have been confined to the academic realm with a focus on composites and thickeners in food applications. Other issues with this feedstock are its reliable sourcing and the difficulty to functionalize or process the material, which hampers its further industrialization.

Other examples of sugar-based macromolecules used at an industrial scale are agarose and alginic acid, or alginate, (**Figure 3**) both obtained from algae. Agarose, a polysaccharide made of galactose and 3,6-anhydro-L-galactopyranose, is contained in agar or agar-agar, a substance used extensively for the gelation and thickening of food or in electrophoresis gels in biology. Alginic acid, or its alginate salts, is a polysaccharide made of manuronate and guluronate subunits and is also used as a thickener in food^[36] and in biomedical applications, such as in hydrogels for wound healing.^[37] Algae and marine biorefineries are receiving increased attention in the scientific literature because of their untapped potential up to date, and could provide a new source of monomers and polymers in the future.^[38,39]

Another relevant fraction of biomass is lignin, which is the biggest source of biogenic aromatics available on Earth. The lignin biopolymer consists of a propylphenolic backbone based on three main building blocks—*p*-coumaryl, coniferyl and

Figure 3. Biomass and other natural resources from which macromolecules can be extracted. The chemical structures of the ones discussed are displayed for each natural macromolecule and, where applicable, the small molecules which can be obtained from the macromolecules are also shown along with the products and applications which can be targeted.

sinapyl alcohols—that end up as the so-called S, G, and H (i.e., syringyl, guaiacyl, and hydroxyphenyl) units in the macromolecule (Figure 3). These units are bonded by a range of well-defined linkages, prevalently the alkyl-aryl ether β -O-4 which can correspond to 60–80% of the interunit linkages in lignin. The percentage of lignin in biomass varies with the source, ranging from 15 up to 50 wt%, and its main role in plants is to protect them against pathogens, confer structural strength, and bind the other components together.^[40,41]

While having very interesting inherent properties (e.g., antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-UV),^[42] the biggest challenge related to the lignin biopolymer is its controlled isolation in a near-native state. Accordingly, native lignin is a reactive macromolecule that tends to form C–C bonds during traditional biorefining processes, yielding complex, polydisperse, and chemically heterogeneous technical lignins (also called industrial lignins) such as Kraft lignin, soda lignin, or lignosulphonates. Technical lignins were historically deemed as a mere residue and mostly burned as a low value energy source for the process (e.g., in pulp and paper industries), but this is fortunately changing thanks to joint efforts from large industries, SMEs, and academia. Even though the properties and complex chemical structure pose challenges to their utilization in high value applications—for instance, the depolymerization of such streams typically leads to low monomer yields and very low selectivity—the use of technical lignins in materials (e.g., polyurethanes, phenol–formaldehyde and epoxy resins), construction (as cement admixtures), fuels, asphalt, animal feed, batteries, among others is getting more and more established.^[42–44] Notable commercial uses of technical lignins such as Kraft and lignosulphonates include binders, phenol replacements in resin applications and dispersing agents (e.g., Lineo, Lignode).^[45,46] While this is a relatively facile and fast way to replace petro-based products with

biobased ones, the current commercial routes using technical lignins target mostly low value applications. Furthermore, full phenol or bisphenol A replacement with lignin in materials could not be yet achieved due to the low performance observed in such cases, which is related to the low reactivity, polydispersity, chemical heterogeneity, and steric hindrance of technical lignins.

To target high performance materials and niche applications, such as fine chemicals and pharmaceuticals from lignin, novel approaches have been developed. As aforementioned, irreversible and uncontrolled pathways happening during traditional biomass processing schemes are responsible for the complex structural features of technical lignins. Recent efforts have focused on preventing such pathways to happen in the first place, and new technologies allow the isolation of noncondensed and well-characterized lignins through the stabilization of reactive intermediates formed during biomass fractionation. Such approaches are known as “lignin first” and target mostly the prevalent and reactive β -O-4 linkage of the lignin biopolymer. Main examples include the reductive catalytic fractionation (RCF) process,^[47–50] organosolv processes using protic solvents such as ethanol and butanol,^[51–53] stabilization of lignin intermediates with diols,^[54–57] and the aldehyde-assisted fractionation (AAF) process, which uses aprotic solvents and an aldehyde as stabilization agent.^[58–60] Overall, these biorefining approaches deconstruct biomass while preventing lignin condensation. The obtained products are typically a cellulose-rich pulp, a liquor containing hemicellulose-derived products, and the lignin biopolymer obtained as a solid precipitate. An exception is the RCF process, which combines lignin depolymerization within biomass fractionation and yields lignin monomers and oligomers as a viscous liquid. These processes are well reported in literature and show promising routes for the development of

fully or near-fully biobased materials from lignin. For instance, depolymerized lignin oils from pilot-scale (50 L batch reactor) RCF were successfully incorporated in polyurethanes and epoxy polymers with superior properties,^[61,62] and the production of a potentially benign bisphenol A from 4-propylsyringol (a prevalent lignin-derived monomer) was recently reported, as well as of alkylcyclohexanols that could serve as precursors for new polyesters and polyamides.^[63,64] The AAF process has shown feedstock flexibility,^[65] promising applications in polyurethanes,^[66] and high yields of valuable monomers in continuous operation.^[67] The technology also allows for an *on-demand* lignin functionalization, which brings several opportunities for the design of high-end materials.^[68,69] Current efforts toward industrialization are ongoing, with important testbeds such as LignoCity^[70] and LignoValue^[71] available for the scale-up of new technologies, combined with the various start-up companies working in the biorefining space.^[72–77] The main challenges in the process scale-up include feedstock and catalyst selection, the harsh conditions typically needed for biomass deconstruction (requiring explosive atmosphere protection called ATEX-rated equipment), the contact of the cellulose pulp with the solid catalyst (in the case of RCF), reactor design, and downstream processing for obtaining pure streams of monomers, oligomers and sugars.^[78] As aforementioned, lignin monomers can be used as building blocks in the engineering of polymers, but their typically high production price—a result of the intensive depolymerization and isolation steps—leads to materials 2–10-fold more expensive than commodity plastics.^[79–81] That being said, such lignin-derived compounds could be competitive economically if high-end precision polymers are targeted.^[82] Importantly, the overall sustainability and biobased content of lignin-derived materials has to be evaluated in a case-by-case basis through life cycle analyses (LCA), as this will largely depend on the nature of the polymerizable group added.^[34]

Cork, produced at more than 300 000 t per year in Europe alone,^[83,84] is another interesting raw material from Nature and is mainly used as cork stoppers for wine, insulation, or floor coverings.^[85] Cork is mainly composed of cellulose, lignin and suberin (Figure 3), all three macromolecules, at 18, 22, and 40 wt%, respectively.^[85] While lignin and cellulose are well known, and their uses have been discussed above, suberin is a polyester whose structure is still elusive.^[86] The main building blocks present in its structure are glycerol, some phenolics, such as ferulic acid, fatty alcohols and fatty acids, ω -hydroxy fatty acids, and α,ω -fatty diacids.^[86] So far, no biorefinery concept or cork valorization project has been able to separate suberin efficiently into these molecules. Nonetheless, a way of producing the aforementioned molecules is interesting from a renewable feedstock perspective as they are typically sold at a high price and in demand for the polymer and chemical industries. Three further factors make cork an interesting biomass to work with: i) the corking process of a tree produces a significant amount of cork waste, as only the mature cork after 40 years and two previous harvests can be used,^[87] ii) the wine industry is moving to other types of stoppers, so that a novel valorization of cork would be highly market driven, and iii) removing cork or the bark from the tree does not harm its growth. However, the regional dependence and the relatively high price of cork, may hamper an efficient use of this raw material.

3. Bottom-Up: Monomers and Their Biopolymers

Apart from the macromolecules that can be isolated from biomass, a multitude of small molecules can be obtained as well, such as terpenes, fats and oils, and hemicellulosic sugars (Figure 4). These can make up to 40% of the overall plant mass and are thus non-negligible fractions when it comes to the full valorization of biomass. A major difference of this and the above-mentioned natural macromolecules is that these have already been in use for centuries in high-value applications, such as essential oils and medicine. The extraction, and especially purification, of these molecules is feasible industrially, however these processes are typically rather expensive to perform, leading to higher prices. In addition, most plants contain only small amounts of these molecules, i.e., terpenes in less than 5% of dry plant mass,^[88] or are only present in large amounts in the seeds or fruits of the plant, i.e., ricinoleic acid in castor beans, which means such plants need to be specifically grown taking away arable land for food. Therefore, such renewable building blocks are more suited for low volumes specialty polymers than commodity plastics. The polymers possible from such feedstocks have been previously summarized for terpenes^[89–93] and fatty acids,^[16,94–100] and range from polyethers to polyurethanes. These polymers could replace petrol-based analogues as foams, curing agents, or adhesives. So far however, there is no large-scale commercial plant or even plan to produce terpene or fatty acid-based polymers in the future.

Other small molecules which are obtained in almost all biorefineries are xylose, and other hemicellulosic sugars, such as arabinose and mannose (Figure 4). Although a macromolecule in plants, the pretreatment that is applied to biomass deconstructs this polysaccharide into its sugar building blocks. One major advantage of this type of side stream is that xylose, arabinose, and mannose are nonedible sugars and thus do not compete with food. In addition, many processes already produce hemicellulosic waste streams at a multiton scale, oftentimes in aqueous solutions, and thus the use of such underutilized streams is of huge interest for the agricultural and pulp and paper industry. Most investigations have looked at the enzymatic or fermentative valorization of the hemicellulosic feedstock mainly on xylose, as it is by far the most abundant sugar obtained from hemicellulose at around 30 wt% within certain biomasses.^[101,102] A variety of studies have looked at synthesizing monomers from these feedstocks and include monomers with ring structures, such as oxetanes^[103] or carbonates,^[104] monomer diesters,^[105] or monomers bearing an unsaturation, e.g., acrylates.^[33,106,107] The most promising ones use few, high-yielding steps to get from the sugars to the monomer and only add bio-based functionalities (if any) and thus preserve the inherent renewability of the sugars. From these monomers, a multitude of polymers have been obtained, such as polyesters,^[105,108] polycarbonates,^[104] and polyethers.^[108] One challenge of all these approaches is that they use pure xylose, which is an expensive raw material. A more realistic scenario to produce cost-competitive monomers and polymers would be to start from already existing waste xylose streams, such as sugar cane residue. The downside of such streams is that they need to be dewatered and purified prior to use, in turn increasing the price. This is akin to lignin monomers, which could be potentially used as building blocks for polymer engineering

Figure 4. Chemical structures of the main small bio-based molecules available from biomass which can be used as building blocks for various polymers.

(vide supra), a route typically hampered by their high production cost.^[63,109]

4. Remaining Challenges

Despite the significant advances that have been achieved, challenges remain for natural macromolecules and lignocellulosic biomass-derived monomers. One huge aspect is the upscaling process that needs to be considered already at the lab scale, to avoid technical and process issues later down the line. For example, no process which is atom inefficient and generates more waste than product is scalable to industrial levels because of economic and efficiency considerations, and such issues need to be addressed right from the start. Several different tools exist to highlight such hurdles early on and most rely on the principles of Green Chemistry,^[110,111] such as the environmental factor (E-factor).^[112]

Equally important is the ability to obtain pure molecules or products from the processes and reaction mixtures. Academic papers often focus on yields which are theoretical and not isolated, but the separation of such mixtures oftentimes constitutes a major challenge in the upscaling and commercialization process. Not only does the separation pose a technological challenge but it also strongly impacts the price of the molecules and products that can be obtained from a biorefinery. The main driver for the latter is the energy consumption of separation techniques which are often left aside during process modeling.^[7] Identifying early on whether mixtures can be separated and how this can be achieved is thus a critical element for any biorefinery research.

An adequate feedstock selection in a biorefinery is another key challenge, as it must be based on its intrinsic properties (e.g., particle size morphology, moisture content, composition, porosity, etc.) but also take into account supply chain aspects. Accordingly, biomass properties can vary substantially among types of plants, soil, season, and location. Furthermore, biomass produc-

tion can be impacted by natural events and plagues, which are difficult to predict and bring a high risk. The logistics can be further complicated in case of bulky feedstocks with low density or high water content—storage/transportation costs and associated CO₂ emissions have to be considered carefully. Overall, the rising demand for biomass and the emerging bioproducts industry have increased the complexity of multilevel supply systems. This creates a need for integrated biomass supply chain (BSC) management approaches that consider all supply chain aspects and uncertainties, as well as addressing different scenarios to de-risk the industrialization of novel biorefinery schemes. A pivotally important task for developing a biorefinery is to create a reliable biomass supply chain for enough feedstock at a stable price. A BSC generally starts at the cultivation level (establishment and treatment of forest plantations and agricultural energy crops), going through harvesting, preprocessing, transportation, handling, and storage, to ultimately end at the final conversion unit such as a biorefinery or bioenergy conversion plant. Unfortunately, the target products in the BSC studies published so far are mainly ethanol, electricity, and heat, with little focus on bio-based chemicals and materials.^[113] This state of the art clearly shows the crucial need for techno-economic analyses dedicated to advanced biorefinery schemes that aim for high-end products (e.g., materials and fine chemicals) besides bioenergy.

A further recurring issue is the, often misunderstood, difference between bio-based and biodegradable, especially for consumers. While all the above examples contain a significant share of bio-based carbons and oxygens and are thus bio-based, they are not necessarily biodegradable.^[114] This leads to confusion on several levels, and can have severe implications for involved stakeholders, such as consumers and industries, and society, e.g., bio-based materials which are not biodegradable are disposed of in Nature. Furthermore, it is important to stress that every application is different and that materials and products to which only one applies, bio-based or biodegradable, or to which both apply,

bio-based and biodegradable, are needed and that one is not necessarily better or worse than the other. Only a rigorous LCA would allow for conclusions on the sustainability of one option over the other to be drawn. This also highlights the need for robust standards and guidelines in the biorefinery space, as LCAs are often-times difficult to compare because of their assumptions and the different methodologies used.^[7,115,116]

Along with this comes the regulatory framework, which does not move as fast as technologies or novel products and thus delays their market entry. For instance, the norms for “natural” ingredient and “naturally derived” ingredient (i.e., *any substance where the starting material is of plant origin but has been chemically processed*) are different and often unclear, particularly for novel compounds. The case of lignin polymer is a remarkable one, as its structural features can vary substantially depending on the process, and proper characterization is challenging. As such, the incorporation of moieties during isolation must be analyzed in detail to determine in which category each specific lignin product fits. Another issue regarding lignin is that the EU biodegradability and compostability standards (e.g., ISO 17556)^[117] are based on degradation to CO₂ within a certain time (e.g., 90% within 6 months). These requirements cannot be met by products made from lignin due to its recalcitrant character—in fact, lignin was designed by Nature to resist microbial attack. Therefore, the current standards need to be updated to include such specificities, as lignin cannot be simply placed in the same regulatory framework as synthetic polymers with similar biodegradation patterns. As the main function of lignin in plants is to resist biodegradation, industry could only benefit from its slow degradation by incorporating lignin in applications that require high durability while avoiding toxicity.

Another important driver of sustainable change is governmental support. For instance, the European Union has several programs dedicated to advancing a bioeconomy and develop technology-based sustainable solutions. These are key for any development in this area as they enable high-risk high-potential ideas and technologies to be financed outside of existing structures or existing financial streams. From an SME perspective, this is a huge aid in the development of technologies for the future from a finance side. It is therefore unsurprising that a multitude of bio-based, biorefinery, or sustainable technologies are currently at the demonstration or industrialization step. Societal pressure plays a major role in this space as well, as advances in technology allowed for an easy access and worldwide distribution of information. Society is, in general, much more aware of topics such as sustainability and climate change, increasing the demand for environmentally responsible practices.

A further driver of future developments and reorientations of industries will be closely linked to the CO₂ price. Currently valued at 84 € per ton,^[118] its highest ever with expectations that it will rise to 150–200 € per ton. The increasing CO₂ price has a big impact on large CO₂ emitting industries, as offsetting their CO₂ emissions will get more and more expensive. Large companies and governments have declared targets of net zero by 2030 or 2050, which they can currently only achieve by offsetting their CO₂ emissions. This will likely be more expensive and thus more difficult, creating an economic driver for change and making it easier for new technologies to gain market shares and for large companies to seek for more sustainable value chains.

5. Conclusion

The use of macromolecules and monomers obtained from biorefineries has received heightened attention over the last two decades. To advance toward a carbon-neutral society, the whole potential of biomass must be valorized and thus each biomass component plays a pivotal role in creating a sustainable and cost-competitive biorefinery. The multidisciplinary of the challenge means that joint collaborations and research and development across fields and sectors is needed. Both the biopolymers as well as the small monomeric building blocks already present in Nature provide multiple opportunities for specialty and commodity polymers as well as everyday materials to be created. Already today, these range from resins and concrete additives to flavors and fragrances. One of the most important aspects is the sourcing of the raw materials—competition with food or arable land must be avoided, and a stable supply of biomass with standard properties and pricing is needed. In addition, market entry and commercialization need to be facilitated by key industrial and governmental players, which are under increasing pressure to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions. Strong process design and technological advances (particularly in terms of hardware, i.e., dedicated equipment and efficient downstream steps) well-aligned with robust LCAs and an up-to-date regulatory framework are paramount to move forward and guarantee the scale-up and industrialization of innovative biorefining schemes.

Overall, the fast developments and commercialization of a variety of biorefineries all over the world are a first sign that biorefineries are already part of the solution to a bio-based economy. The authors therefore strongly believe that biomass will be the resource of the future for all of humankind's materials, just like petroleum is today.

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Conflict of Interest

All of the authors are employees of Bloom Biorenewables SA or are involved in projects in collaboration with this private entity.

Author Contributions

P.B.V.S and M.B.F. assisted in conceptualization, writing original draft, review and editing, and visualization.

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